
SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND PERFORMANCE OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTH-EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated supply chain management practices and performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria. It aimed to assess the influence of strategic supplier partnership, customer relationship, sorting strategy on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms. The researcher employed explanatory research design with a cross-sectional approach design and a targeted population of 250 staff comprising all the marketing staff from 10 different food and beverage (F&B) manufacturing firms in the South East, Nigeria as the area of study where 2 firms from each state were selected that include Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo state. Descriptive analysis employed includes; means, percentages, and standard deviations in describing how strategic supplier partnerships influenced operational performance. The study used structured questionnaire where four point Likert scale was provided for the respondents to score as follows: strongly agree = 4, agree = 3, disagree = 2, strongly disagree = 1. Correlation analysis and regression analysis was employed to establish the relationship between strategic supplier partnerships and operational performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms. The findings revealed that supplier partnership had a strong negative and significant correlation with evident in the correlation coefficient of ($r = -0.690$, $p = 0.000$), the same way customer relationship had a strong negative and significant correlation with evident in the correlation coefficient of ($r = 0.655$, and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$), finally Sorting strategy had a strong negative and significant correlation with evident in the correlation coefficient of ($r = -0.534$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$) in the performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. Practical implications and a future research agenda were presented in light of the limitations of this study.

Keywords: Supply chain management, Strategic supplier partnership, Customer relationship, Sorting strategy and Performance

Introduction

A supply chain is a network of functions or organizations connected through the products and services that they offer in order to deliver them to the end consumer. Crandall Crandall, & Chen (2015) highlights that a simple supply chain consists of participants in a certain order from upstream to downstream. The practices and activities of managing supply chains are known as supply chain management (SCM). Supply chain management can provide a major source of competitive advantage and the goal of a supply chain manager must therefore be to link the end customers, the channels of distribution, the production processes and the procurement activity while according to (Nilipour-Tabatabaei et al., 2012) that the supply chain management (SCM) goal is to share market information, develop new products, improve the number of suppliers for manufacturers, and activate and release management resources to build long-term relationships based on the members' initial trust needs. They are the set of events and activities that happen in an organization to ensure the effective management of the value chain (Truong et al., 2017). The Association of Supply Chain Management (2019) defines SCM as "the design, planning, execution, control, and monitoring of supply chain activities with the objective of creating net value, building a competitive infrastructure, leveraging worldwide logistics, synchronizing supply with demand, and measuring performance globally". The concept of supply chain management has gained the attention of professionals and scholars alike (Chaghooshi et al., 2015) as manufacturing firms all over the world are faced with lots of challenges that impact their performance.

The manufacturing firm as a sector of any country is expected to be the engine growth and base for sustainable improvement and economic development as manufacturing transforms raw materials or components into finished products through various production processes. It encompasses activities such as assembly, fabrication and quality control to ensure the efficient and timely production of goods (Las 2024). The evolution of industries in today's economy hinges on advancements in production technologies, moving from conventional to modern mass production systems through effective management techniques and technological integration (Ayodele & Falokun, 2020). It encompasses traditional craftsmanship and modern high-tech transformations, essential for producing goods and services, creating employment opportunities, and generating significant economic benefits (Sola, Obamuyi & Adekunjo, 2017). This is for the fact that it has potentials for creating stream of income, employment opportunity, revenue generation to the government, poverty alleviation and above all it can change the structure of economy. It becomes imperative for Nigeria to develop its manufacturing sub-sector in order to achieve meaningful transformation and sustainable development. The performance of Nigerian manufacturing sector as a whole down to South East since independent is not encouraging especially in the area of serving as a catalyst for industrialization and economic growth.

Much of the current theoretical/empirical research in supply chain management focuses on the downstream or upstream supply chain or certain SCM characteristics (For instance, Clark & Lee, 2000; Tan, 2002). Shapiro (2001) observed that most manufacturing firms have seen little or no impact in the supply chain management practices because they either focus only on their supplier and customer, forgetting that there must be an alignment between supply

chain management practices and company strategy (strategic choice). Supply chain management and advancement in technology often pose problems which arise as a result of outdated systems, lack of integration between different platforms, data silos, limited scalability and cyber security vulnerabilities. These issues can lead to inefficiencies, errors in data management, operational disruptions and compromised data security. There's a lot of inherent risk in supply chain that include Supplier bankruptcies, theft, new government regulations, natural disasters, cyber security vulnerabilities and any of these risk factors could severely disrupt your supply chain management and impact your bottom line. Both known and unknown risks will always be in play, which is why supply chain risk management is most time difficult to handle in manufacturing firms.

Despite efforts made by different Governments to improve on manufacturing firms and move the economic base of Nigeria from monoculture relying on oil sector to industrial base, the industrial sector has not impacted very positively on the national economic development. The major factors responsible for retrogression of Nigerian manufacturing sub-sector can be attributed to the Poor State of electricity supply, unfriendly business environment. The Nigerian business environment is far from been friendly for manufacturing activities to thrive. A poor critical infrastructure to support the sector, import of essential raw materials is always big challenge and government bureaucracy is very cumbersome (MAN, 1991). The established industries relied heavily on imported raw materials. Infrastructural Challenges; Nigeria's infrastructural challenges are so daunting that they have caused incalculable damage to the growth of the economy in general and manufacturing sub-sector in particular. It becomes imperative for Nigeria to develop its manufacturing sub-sector in order to achieve meaningful transformation and sustainable development. In reality successive governments, Nigeria have not made earnest adequate investments in public infrastructures to required level for achieving sustainable economic growth. The challenges of manufacturing firms include market instability, high cost of raw material and energy abound in the sector.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study was to examine supply chain management practices and performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of strategic supplier partnership on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria
- ii. Determine the influence of customer relationship on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria
- iii. Examine the influence of sorting strategy on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria

Literature review

Recent studies highlight Supply chain management impact on firm performance across various industries, emphasizing practices like supplier collaboration and information sharing (Kadiane, Zhang, & Shib, 2023; Çetindaş et al., 2023). Supply chain management includes the planning and execution of the whole flow of a good or service. Along with the

technological advancement, supply chain management creates an entirely new business environment for the manufacturing organizations (Mentzer, 2004). Essentially, supply chain management oversees the end-to-end processes involved in the production and distribution of goods or services, from raw material sourcing to delivery to the end customer. It encompasses various activities such as procurement, manufacturing, logistics and inventory management, with the goal of optimizing efficiency, reducing costs and meeting customer demand. Firm performance, the outcome of effective SCM, evaluates operational success and organizational goals achievement (Alahmad, 2021; Green et al., 2012). Scholars have defined SCM and its practices. Obi, and Ehiedu, (2020); Onuorah, Ehiedu Victor, and Okoh, (2021); Odita and Ehiedu and Kifordu (2020); Odita, and Ehiedu, (2015); Mentzer, Flint, and Hult (as cited in Mutuerandu, 2014) defined SCM as "a group of three or more entities (organizational or individuals) directly involved in the upstream or downstream flow of products, SCM is the design, planning, execution, control, and monitoring of supply chain activities to create net value, construct a competitive infrastructure, leverage worldwide logistics, synchronize supply with demand, and measure global performance. In this context, Connelly, Ketchen and Hult (2013) point out that supply chain management (SCM) in recent years deserves greater attention because the globalization has significant effects on the supply chains. Therefore, improving supply chain performance is a fundamental approach for achieving competitive advantages of companies (Cai, Liu, Liu, & Xiao, 2009) as businesses rely on a network of suppliers and supporting services to move their products from raw materials to final "last-mile" delivery to customers. These suppliers form "links" in your supply chain. Effective supply chain management involves strategic planning, coordination, and collaboration with suppliers, partners and stakeholders to ensure seamless operations and customer satisfaction. The existence of supply chain highlights the need for firms to not only acknowledge upstream and downstream business entities but to also build sustainable and mutually beneficial relationships with their upstream and downstream partners (Lambert, Knemeyer & Gardner, 2004). To form a positive relationship between a firm's rates of performance improvement and the level of integration between the firm and the firm's suppliers and customers need to be seen as part of the system of the manufacturing company (Frohlich & Westbrook 2001)

Manufacturing Firm performance is mediated by an interplay of many factors, which can be categorized as internal and external business environmental factors. Samad (2022) noted that internal resources such as innovation capabilities and external factors such as technology and the environmental system positively affect firm performance. This means that firms that want to achieve the ultimate performance must exploit their available resources, for example, by applying innovative technology to their products, processes, and markets (Hung and Chou, 2013). The holistic application of innovative technology in business operations is recognized as operational innovation in this study and expressed by Hammer (2004) as the only certain way of gaining lasting superior performance. In this case, operational innovation would provide opportunities for businesses to enter specific markets by helping them obtain sources of competitive advantage, which influences firm performance (Hou et al., 2019). The Nigeria food and beverage market is segmented into six regions: North Central, North East, North West, South East, South, and South West. Each region presents unique opportunities and challenges for market players, driven by differences in demographics, economic conditions, and consumer preferences. The South West region, which includes Lagos, is the largest and

most developed market, characterized by a high population density, significant urbanization, and higher disposable incomes. The South East region being the researcher focus is known for its entrepreneurial spirit, as rise small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the food and beverage sector is seen through distribution channels, such as traditional open markets and roadside vendors as it continue to play a vital role in the Nigeria food and drink market. These channels are particularly important in rural and semi-urban areas where modern retail infrastructure is limited. Open make in the South East offer a variety of fresh produce, local foods, and traditional delicacies, often at competitive prices. Roadside vendors provide convenient access to snacks, beverages, and ready-to-eat foods, catering to the needs of commuters and busy individuals. Despite the growth of organized retail, these traditional channels remain integral to the food and drink ecosystem in Nigeria. The South East regions are also noteworthy for their rapid urbanization and economic expansion. The South East region, with its entrepreneurial spirit, is witnessing the growth of SMEs in the food and beverage sector, contributing to a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 6.5% (dataintelo.com 2023). According to (Dataintelo.com 2023), the global market size for the Nigeria food and beverage industry was valued at USD 50 billion, with a forecaster growth to USD 90 billion by 2032. This robust growth is primarily fueled by increasing disposable incomes, urbanization, and changing consumer preferences towards convenience and processed foods. The market is witnessing substantial investments in infrastructure, technology, and retail innovations to cater to the evolving consumer demands. Furthermore, Nigeria's economic reforms and government initiatives aimed at improving agricultural productivity have significantly boosted the food and beverage sector. Policies such as the Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP) and incentives for local food production aim to reduce dependency on imports and enhance food security. These efforts have encouraged investments in food processing industries, fostering local production and reducing prices, making food products more accessible to the average consumer. Additionally, the government's focus on improving infrastructure, such as transportation and storage facilities and has facilitated better market linkages and supply chain efficiencies. The Nigeria food and beverages market is segmented into two main product types: food and beverages. The food segment encompasses a wide range of products, including staples such as rice, maize, and wheat, as well as processed foods, snacks, and ready-to-eat meals. This segment is driven by the increasing demand for convenience foods as busy lifestyles and urbanization take center stage, The beverage segment includes both alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks such as water, soft drinks, juices, coffee, tea, beer, wine, and spirits. The growth in this segment is attributed to the rising disposable incomes, changing consumer lifestyles, and increasing awareness about health and wellness. The South East and South regions are experiencing rapid urbanization and economic growth, leading to increased demand for food and beverage products.

Strategic supplier partnership and management performance

Strategic supplier partnership improves the capacity of each participant and is important in aligning the firm towards the direction of achieving potential benefits (Kushwaha & Sharma, 2016). This is defined as the long term relationship between an organization and its suppliers. It is designed to leverage the strategic and operational capabilities of individual participating in organizations to help them achieve significant ongoing benefits (Tan, 2002). While

encouraging problem solution and common strategic planning, strategic supplier partnerships allows the firm to target on long-term objectives. They rely on sharing the contribution and responsibilities of each party thereby enabling a more efficient environment. Strategic supplier partnerships improves the capacity of individuals in the supply chain and directs the firm towards the direction of re-achieving potential benefits that pertains to operational performance (Naveed, 2016). They promote mutual benefit and inclusion in important policy areas of procurement and supply chain management. Kellner and Lasch (2016) noted that strategic supplier partnerships rely on sharing the contribution and responsibilities of each party thereby enabling a more efficient environment. Suppliers can help measure product design which leads to establishing the best technical and economical need for production. Strategic supplier partnerships are effective when the links between supply chain partners are doing the best and thus the more effective firms are internally, the more effective their supply chain will be. Strategic supplier partnership is obtained through the proper application of technology and partnerships. Through this practice, the supply chain can determine how best to meet the demands of the marketplace (Ola & Limberg, 2011). In terms of food and beverage manufacturing firms Kushwaha and Sharma (2016) opined that they are encountering competition and pressure to reduce lead times and product prices. The ever-changing markets demand more unique innovations with higher quality products and processes. As such, food and beverage manufacturing companies in the south East Nigeria need to improve supplier involvement in relation to product development processes. Collaboration between manufacturers and supply chain partners at the product development process contributes to production of products that best meet the customer needs (Naveed, 2016).

Customer relationship and Management performance

The study of the relationship between customer relationship management (CRM) and the outcomes of organization (such as performance, turnover, assets base and improvement in the number of customers, among others) has been extensively researched. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has emerged to be among of the most rapidly expanding business technology solutions in the past decade. As such, it is an essential tool for businesses looking to achieve long-term, sustainable commercial success (Guerola-Navarro et al., 2021). CRM become a focus of scientific research, (Foltean et al., 2019; Gil-Gomez et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2021; Guerola-Navarro et al., 2020; Soltani et al., 2018; Rahimi & Kozak, 2017; Sofi et al., 2020) because CRM is a crucial business practice used to manage interactions between a company and its customers (Das & Hassan, 2022; Haislip & Richardson, 2017; Dalla Pozza et al., 2018). In line with the above contentions, (Kim, Suh and Hwang, 2003) showed that CRM can be improved due to social entities initiated by marketing strategies, implying that brands are sources of value for CRM and thus influence consumer which is aimed at improving organizational performance. Customer relationship management in the food and beverage firms is viewed on how organizations offer the best products to their customers to maintain and retain a good relationship with them. Zablah (2015) emphasized five points of view for defining Customer relationship management (Process, strategy, Philosophy, ability and technology). Rababah, Mohd and Ibrahim, (2020) opined that customer relationship management is the working of a customer-oriented culture by which a

strategy is made for gaining, upgrading and holding of customers which is powered by an information technology application. Kotler and Armstrong (2015) defined CRM as the overall process of building and maintaining profitable customer relationships by delivering superior customer value and satisfaction. This definition seems to include the broad-based essence of marketing, wherein value and satisfaction are prominent. The main goals of Customer relationship management are to value long-lasting supportive relationships with the old customers and the upcoming customers. The company will always want to retain those customers for continuous transaction that will bring increase in the performance of the organization and the end result is profitability (Adelina et al., 2020). Customer relationship management is a comprehensive strategy and method of recruiting, retaining, and forming partnerships with targeted customers to provide higher value for the organization and the customer, it is centered on gathering data prior to decisions making and focuses on enhancing, maintaining, and developing long-term relationships with clients (Pakdaman et al., 2013)

Sorting strategy and management performance

There are two components to the term strategic sourcing, namely “strategic” & “sourcing”. “Sourcing,” as defined by Benson and Ribbers (2020), is a procurement function on how an organization will acquire the resources for its business activities, whereas “strategic” refers to how the organization plans to manage vendors for the said sourcing purpose. Strategic sourcing is key for successful global supply chain management. As the core challenge of supply chain management is the removal of barriers between the organization and its suppliers and customers in order to maintain customer service excellence, financial position improvement, and operational costs optimization, strategic sourcing emerges as an important factor to support and integrate the suppliers into the supply chain intelligently. According to Chiang et al. (2011) is a critical challenge of designing and managing supply networks in line with the organizations operational and performance objectives. Strategic sourcing has been proven to be affective and result in cost reduction, increases in productivity, quality improvement, and return on investment. Considering sourcing as strategic has been considered as a driver for company growth. Strategic sourcing allows an organization to shares information with its suppliers in real time with the aim of cutting the cost of materials, minimizing inventory, reducing shortages, and expediting deliveries (Van Weele, 2010). Strategic sourcing can reduce costs by consolidating purchases with a limited number of suppliers and by allowing the centralized purchasing departments negotiating leverage via a purchase of increased volume. Strategic sourcing can also help reduce ordering costs of purchasing orders thus reducing inventory handling costs (Thomas, 1999; Rendon, 2005; Van Weele, 2010). It promotes cross-functional, intra- and inter-organizational integration (Chen et al., 2004) considering short- and long-term orientation. On one hand, it is worth commoditizing goods and services using a matrix, and trying to standardize complex negotiation (Vitasek, 2018) in order to reduce procurement variability and try to increment procurement governance. The decision to outsource or revert to outsourcing decisions (by purchasing from the local market or re-shoring, i.e. bringing previously off-shored items or services back to the country of origin), or to extend cost appraisal, consider consumer preference, availability and quality of raw material or skilled labor, access to domestic

markets, and government incentives. As Strategic Sourcing incorporate strategic dimensions and capabilities of suppliers such as emphasis on quality management practices, process capabilities, design and development, and cost reduction capabilities into the decision-making process it is possible for firms to achieve accurate information and best-in class market results (Beaty, 2013). Van Weele (2010) is of the view that when conducting a plan for strategic sourcing there are some aspects to consider, such as technology, quality, availability, cost and fulfillment. Considering sourcing as strategic has been considered as a driver for company growth. Strategic sourcing allows an organization to shares information with its suppliers in real time with the aim of cutting the cost of materials, minimizing inventory, reducing shortages, and expediting deliveries (Van Weele, 2010).

Theoretical Framework

Resource-Based Theory

Resource-Based Theory (RBT) was first put forward by Penrose (2009), who proposed a model on the effective management of firms' resources, diversification strategy, and productive opportunities. Penrose's publication was the first to propose conceptualizing a firm as a coordinated bundle of resources to address and tackle how it can achieve its goals and strategic behaviour (Penrose, 2009; Penrose, 2009). RBT began to take shape in the 1980s. The antecedent of RBT was the Theory of the Growth of the Firm. Later, during the 1990s, Jay Barney's (1991) work was critical to the emergence of RBT and became the dominant paradigm in strategic management and strategic planning. The resource-based theory (RBT) is an influential approach in strategic management. It has been widely applied as a managerial framework to determine vital resources for a firm to achieve a sustained competitive advantage. The theory provides an essential framework to explain and predict the fundamentals of a company's performance and competitive advantage. Moreover, in the past 20 years, this dimension of performance and/or organizational competitiveness has been analyzed under the angle of the resource-based Theory (RBT). According to this theory, the competitiveness of any organization is based on the resources it masters to develop core competencies. RBT provides a framework to highlight and predict the fundamentals of organization performance and competitive advantage. The focus of RBT on the firm's performance based on many perspectives was a reaction to the earlier managerial interest in the industry structure, a more macro perspective. RBT addresses an internally-driven approach by focusing on internal organization resources, as opposed to externally driven approaches to understanding the accomplishment or failure of leveraging transnational activities (Kozlenkova, Samaha & Palmatier, 2014). It aims to elaborate on imperfectly imitable firm resources that could potentially become the source of sustained competitive advantage (Barney, 1991).

Relevant of the Theory to the Study

Resource-Based Theory, RBT focuses attention on an origination's resources as a means of organizing processes and obtaining a competitive advantage. it is a managerial framework used to determine the strategic resources a firm can exploit to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. By applying RBT to supply chain studies, researchers and practitioners can gain a deeper understanding of resources and capabilities that drive supply chain success and develop strategies to leverage these resources to achieve sustainable competitive advantage

and enhancing the performance of a manufacturing firms through its manager and gaining a deeper understanding of the resources and capabilities that drive manufacturing success and develop strategies to leverage these resources to achieve sustainable competitive advantage.

Empirical review

Mwangi (2019) researched on the influence of supply chain optimization on the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. The findings indicated that elements of supply chain optimization influenced manufacturing firms' performance. Specifically, the study revealed that the relationship between inventory controls, supplier management, and procurement cost optimization, supply chain automation and performance of manufacturing firms was significant. Furthermore, the staff competence had a moderating effect on the association between supply chain optimization and performance. Gupta (2019) investigated the mediating role of supply chain integration in the relationship between strategic sourcing and cost reduction within manufacturing companies. Recognizing the interconnected nature of supply chain processes, the researchers aimed to explore how effective integration of suppliers and internal processes enhances the cost-saving potential of strategic sourcing initiatives. Through a combination of quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, they examined the interplay between strategic sourcing practices, supply chain integration, and cost reduction outcomes. The findings of their study suggested that companies with high levels of supply chain integration were better positioned to realize cost reduction benefits from strategic sourcing initiatives. Moreover, the study identified specific mechanisms through which supply chain integration facilitates cost reduction, including improved communication, coordination, and information sharing across supply chain partners. However, it's essential for companies to address potential barriers to supply chain integration, such as organizational silos, legacy systems, and cultural resistance, to unlock the full potential of strategic sourcing for cost reduction. Smith (2017) explored the impact of strategic sourcing practices on cost reduction in a diverse sample of manufacturing firms. The researchers employed a survey methodology to collect data from a wide range of manufacturing companies operating in various industries. Through statistical analysis, they examined the relationship between the implementation of strategic sourcing strategies and cost reduction outcomes. The findings of their study revealed a significant positive correlation between the adoption of strategic sourcing practices and the achievement of cost reduction objectives within manufacturing organizations. Moreover, the study identified specific strategic sourcing techniques such as supplier consolidation, negotiation strategies, and supplier relationship management as key drivers of cost reduction. By elucidating the link between strategic sourcing and cost reduction, the study provided valuable insights for manufacturing companies. Onyango, Kiruri, and Karanja (2015) conducted a study on the effect of strategic supplier relationship management on internal operational performance of manufacturing firms. The findings showed that the strategic supplier relationship management affected the performance. Business-supplier communication and business-supplier joint decision making both individually and jointly have positive effect on internal operational performance.

Methodology

The researcher employed explanatory research design with a cross-sectional approach. This research design goes beyond description of a phenomenon by attempting to explain reasons for a given phenomenon that a descriptive study only observes (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The targeted population comprised all the marketing staff in 10 different food and beverage (F&B) manufacturing firms in the South East Nigeria as the area of study, 2 firms from each state that include Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo state. The study therefore targeted all the marketing staff in the 10 different F&B manufacturing firms. Descriptive analysis employed includes; means, percentages, and standard deviations in describing how strategic supplier partnerships influenced operational performance. On the other hand, inferential analysis employed correlation analysis and regression analysis to establish the relationship between strategic supplier partnerships and operational performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms.

Question 1: What is the influence of strategic supplier partnerships on operational performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria?

Table 1: Influence of Strategic Supplier Partnerships on Operational Performance

		Strategic supplier partnership	Performance of F & B manufacturing firms
Strategic Supplier Partnerships	Pearson Correlation	1	-.690**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	220	220
Performance of F & B manufacturing firms	Pearson Correlation	-.690**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	220	220

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Author's computation using SPSS version, 2025

The result of correlation analysis indicated that strategic supplier partnership performance on food and beverages manufacturing firms had a strong negative and significant correlation with supply chain management practices in South East, Nigeria ($r = -0.690$, $p = 0.000$). The findings imply that, increase in supply chain management practices results in decrease in strategic supplier partnerships and a decrease in supply chain management practices would lead to supply chain management practices among firms in the study area. The $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ signifies a statistically significant relationship between strategic supplier partnerships and supply chain management practices. This finding is in line with Kushwaha & Sharma, (2016) who posited that strategic supplier partnership improves the capacity of each participant and is important in aligning the firm towards the direction of achieving potential benefits

Question 2: What is the influence of customer relationship on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria?

Table 2: Customer relationship on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms

		Customer relationship	Performance of F & B manufacturing firms
Customer Relationship	Pearson Correlation	1	.655**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	220	220
Performance of F & B Manufacturing firms	Pearson Correlation	.655**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Author's computation using SPSS version, 2025

The result of correlation analysis showed that customer relationship had a strong positive and significant correlation with the performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria, hence ($r = 0.655$, and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The findings implied that increase in customer relationship also leads to increases in performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms and similarly, increase in customer relationship results to increase in the search for performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms. The findings concur with Rababah, Mohd and Ibrahim, (2020) that customer relationship management is the working of a customer-oriented culture by which a strategy is made for gaining, upgrading and holding of customers.

Question 3: What is the influence of Sorting Strategy on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria?

Table 3: Sorting Strategy on performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms

		Sorting strategy	Performance of F & B manufacturing firms
Sorting strategy	Pearson Correlation	1	.534**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	220	220
Performance of F&B Manufacturing firms	Pearson Correlation	-.534**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	220	220**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Author's computation using SPSS version, 2025

The result of correlation analysis showed that sorting strategy had a strong negative and significant correlation with performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria ($r = -0.534$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The findings implied that increase in performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms result in decrease of Sorting strategy as the firms might have been established and stable. Similarly, a decrease in performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms to increase Sorting strategy

among firms as supply chain management practices would be required to get more closer to customers thus enhancing sorting strategy. This finding concurs with Van Weele (2010) who is of the view that strategic sourcing allows an organization to shares information with its suppliers in real time with the aim of cutting the cost of materials, minimizing inventory, reducing shortages, and expediting deliveries.

Conclusion

The study revealed and indicated that strategic supplier partnership performance on food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria had a strong negative and significant correlation with evident in the correlation coefficient of ($r = -0.690$, $p = 0.000$). More so, the correlation analysis showed that customer relationship had a strong positive and significant correlation with the performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria with evident in the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.655$, and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The study also concluded that Sorting strategy had a strong negative and significant correlation with performance of food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria with evident in the correlation coefficient ($r = -0.534$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). This result further affirmed the results from the tested hypotheses on the relationships between the dimensions and measures of the predictor and criterion variables.

Recommendation

- i. It is essential for food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria to formalize sustainable supply chain activities by integrating sustainable procurement and reverse logistics strategies into their strategic plans and enforcing strict guidelines.
- ii. It is imperative for food and beverages manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria to develop products that are environmentally friendly, sustainable and regularly reviewed and evaluate supply chain performance to identify areas for improvement.

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